

Adsorption of Propionic Acid at Mercury-Solution Interface from KCl and KBr Solutions : Part I

K. M. Joshi, M. R. Bapat and S. W. Dhawale

Using a precision capillary electrometer, electrocapillary data for various concentrations of propionic acid in decimolar KCl and KBr solutions is reported. The data has been analysed to obtain the variation of charge at interface with potential. Surface excess of the organic acid is estimated as a function of concentration and potential of the cell. Comparing the adsorption of propionic acid from KCl and KBr solutions, it is observed that propionic acid is more adsorbed in the former case at the same potential and concentration.

The study of adsorption of organic acids and organic ions at mercury-solution interface has assumed considerable importance in recent years, ¹⁻⁵ as these lead to the understanding of important electro-organic reactions. Adsorption of organic acids from HClO₄ and HCl has been reported by Miller⁶ and Hansen *et al.*⁷ and by Blomgren, Bockris and Jesch,⁸ and free energy of adsorption has been estimated from capacitance data. Blomgren, Bockris and Jesch have reported the adsorption of valeric acid on mercury from aqueous solution of HCl and have utilised a model for the adsorption of the organic substance based on the replacement of water dipoles at the electrode by organic molecules. Conway⁹ has studied the adsorption of organic aromatic bases and has tried to fit a model based on the dipole-dipole interaction at the interface. The present paper deals with the adsorption of propionic acid at mercury-solution interface from KBr and KCl solutions. The presence of Br⁻ and Cl⁻ ions in the solution causes these to be adsorbed due to specific forces in the Helmholtz layer at the interface between mercury and solution. The adsorption of organic molecule takes place when the Br⁻ or Cl⁻ ions are still adsorbed on the surface. It was therefore thought interesting to investigate the effect of specifically adsorbed hal-ions on the adsorption of organic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

The electrolytic cell comprised of three compartments; one containing the capillary, a reference calomel electrode and an auxiliary platinum electrode. Compartments were

1. R. Parsons. "Modern Aspects of Electrochemistry", Ed. J. O'M. Bockris and B. E. Conway. (Butterworths, London, 1954), Vol. 1, p. 103.
2. A. N. Frumkin and B. B. Damaskin. "Modern Aspects of Electrochemistry", Ed. J. O'M. Bockris and B. E. Conway. (Butterworths, London, 1964), Vol. 3.
3. M. A. V. Devanathan and B. V. S. K. R. A. Tilak, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, **65**, 635.
4. M. R. Bapat, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Bombay, 1968.
5. S. W. Dhawale, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Bombay, 1968.
6. I. R. Miller, *Electrochimica Acta.*, 1966, **9**, 1453.
7. R. S. Hansen, R. E. Minturn and D. A. Hickson, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, **60**, 1185 and 1957, **61**, 953.
8. E. Blomgren, J. O'M. Bockris and C. Jesch, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, **65**, 2000.
9. R. E. Conway and R. G. Barradas, *Electrochimica Acta.*, 1961, **5**, 349.

separated by glass stop-cocks. The capillary was made from pyrex glass. It was so fine that it could withstand a pressure of 30 cm of mercury when dipped in conductivity water. Central compartment was provided with an inlet tube for forcing the solution into the cell as well as for bubbling an inert gas (nitrogen) through the solution for deoxygenation. It was also provided with an optically plane glass window for observing the capillary by means of a microscope (magnification 17.5). The capillary was sealed to a reservoir and could be fitted to the central compartment through a ground glass joint. Central compartment

was also provided with an outlet through a trap. Length of the capillary was so adjusted that it came right in the centre of the window. Reference electrode compartment contained a special type of saturated calomel electrode which eliminated the diffusion of saturated KCl solution into the outer compartment. Auxiliary platinum electrode was prepared by fusing 1×1 cm platinum foil in a pyrex glass tubing through a platinum wire of 0.5 mm thickness. The auxiliary and the reference electrodes were provided with ground glass

joints to avoid air leaking in the experimental solution. Capillary, cell and electrodes were cleaned with concentrated nitric acid followed by clear chromic-sulphuric acid mixture, washed with equilibrium water and dried with dust free air.

To maintain constant temperature entire cell was thermostatted in an air thermostat. It was prepared from hard asbestos sheets and was provided with two compartments, one for mounting cell and other for heating elements and circulating devices. Temperature was adjusted to $33.5^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$ by a Jumo Relay and a contact thermometer. Thermostat was supplied with appropriate glass windows so as to observe and rectify the errors to achieve best thermostatic conditions.

Pressure on the mercury was varied by means of an air leak and an air pump which was connected through a reservoir of one liter capacity which helped to stabilise the pressure. A special micromanipulator¹⁰ was provided for micro adjustments. Pressure was measured by a mercury-manometer. To avoid the error due to curved mercury meniscus, the diameter of the manometer tubing was 1 cm. Sticking of mercury to the manometer tubing was

FIG. 2

10. K. M. Joshi and R. Parsons, *Electrochimica Acta.*, 1961, 4, 129.

overcome by oscillating the mercury by blowing into the open end of the manometer through a CaCl_2 trap. Manometric readings were taken by a cathetometer whose least count was 0.001 cm. Commercial nitrogen used for deoxygenating the solution was purified by passing through alkaline pyrogallol solution and then through concentrated sulphuric acid, water, soda lime, glass wool and over copper turnings at about 450° . It was bubbled through the same solution as in the cell before entering the cell. Cell and nitrogen purification system were bridged by a glass tubing, the ends of which were provided with ground glass joints. Solutions were transferred into the cell under nitrogen atmosphere. The polarising circuit consisted of two wire wound potentiometers connected in series; and were connected across 3 volt battery. An arrangement was also made to change the direction of current. Potentials of the mercury electrode were measured against a saturated calomel electrode by means of a Radiometer—*pH*-meter with an input impedance of 12 megohms. This meter was checked against a calibrated potentiometer before it was used for recording the potentials. Saturated calomel electrode was prepared by standard method and was checked against a set of calomel electrodes agreeing within 1 mv between themselves before and after each experiment.

Chemicals : Mercury was purified by bubbling air through mercury in a flask containing 1% mercurous nitrate and 0.1 *N* HNO_3 solution. It was then washed several times with equilibrium water. After drying it was distilled in "Hulett-Still"¹¹ at 2 cm pressure and then redistilled twice in vacuum. Distilled water was redistilled in pyrex glass assembly over KOH and KMnO_4 . Distillation system was provided with adequate splash traps. Conductivity water, thus obtained, was checked every time for its conductance.

B.D.H. Analar KCl and KBr were recrystallised twice from equilibrium water and only middle fraction was collected, dried and stored in vacuum desiccator for investigation. B.D.H. Analar propionic acid was distilled thrice collecting the middle fraction at 141.1° each time.

11. G. A. Hulett, *Phys. Rev.*, 1905, **21**, 388 and 1911, **33**, 307.

Procedure : Solution under investigation was admitted to the cell under nitrogen atmosphere and was deoxygenated by passing purified nitrogen. It was then allowed to attain a constant temperature of 33.5°. Potential was then applied between the capillary and the auxiliary electrode, as a result of which the position of mercury meniscus in the capillary was changed which was then brought to the reference mark near the tip by applying or releasing pressure on the mercury in the reservoir. The mercury meniscus was illuminated by a 6 volt bulb so as to get a clear view of it, through the microscope. Pressure was read on the manometer using a cathetometer. Readings were taken at every 50 mv interval from 0 to -1100 mv (relative to saturated calomel electrode). Heights of mercury in reservoir and of solution above the reference point were recorded. Total pressure applied at each setting of potential was computed as the total manometric difference plus the height of mercury in the reservoir from the reference point, minus the height of solution (in terms of mercury). Capillary was calibrated using 0.1 M KClO₄ solution. A smooth curve of the total pressure in terms of cm of mercury and the potential was drawn. The surface tension of mercury at the maximum for such a system was known from earlier work,¹² as 423.5 dynes per cm which was used for converting the rest of the pressure values to interfacial tension values.

FIG. 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Relation between interfacial tension, potential and adsorption at constant pressure and temperature is given by Gibbs adsorption equation,

$$-d\gamma = q^M dE - \sum \Gamma_i d\mu_i \quad \dots (1)$$

where γ is the interfacial tension in dynes per cm, q^M is the charge on the mercury in coulombs per cm², E is the potential of the mercury electrode with reference to an electrode reversible to an anion in the solution, Γ_i is the relative surface excess in moles per cm² of the

i th component and μ_i is the chemical potential of i th component. In the present case the system can be represented as

so that equation 1 becomes

$$-d\gamma = q^M dE^- + \Gamma_{acid} d\mu_{acid}^2 + \Gamma_{K^+} d\mu_{salt}^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\text{Since } E^- = E_{cat} + \Delta E$$

where ΔE is the potential of the cell Hg/CaI/KCl//Kx/Hgx/Hg where x is either Cl' or Br' in this case, and the concentration of Kx being 0.1 M,

$$dE^- = dE_{cat} \quad \dots (3)$$

From equation 2 it follows that the charge on the mercury is given by

$$q^M = - \left(\frac{d\gamma}{dE^-} \right)_{\mu_{salt}, \mu_{acid}} \quad \dots (4)$$

while the relative surface excess of acid and K^+ ions is given by

$$\Gamma_{acid} = - \left(\frac{d\gamma}{d\mu_{acid}} \right)_{\mu_{salt}, E^-} \quad \dots (5)$$

and

$$\Gamma_{K^+} = - \left(\frac{d\gamma}{d\mu_{salt}} \right)_{\mu_{acid}, E^-} \quad \dots (6)$$

Electrocapillary data were obtained for six concentrations of propionic acid in 0.1 M KCl solution and for five concentrations in 0.1 M KBr solution over a potential range of 0 mv to -1100 mv with respect to saturated calomel electrode. Electrocapillary curves (γ vs E^-) for KCl and KBr are shown in figures 1 and 2 respectively. Charge on mercury, q^M , was obtained by differentiating the electrocapillary curves at various values of E^- at constant concentration of acid. Variation of charge on the electrode (q^M) with potential is brought out in figures 3 and 4 for KCl and KBr systems respectively. These curves pass through a common inflexion point. The potential of e.c.m. (i.e., $q^M = 0$) for the solution, is seen to shift towards more +ve values with addition of propionic acid, a fact observed by Hansen, Kelsh and Grantham¹³. Values of potentials and interfacial tensions at the point of zero charge for the two systems are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Values of $E_{e.c.m.}$ (relative to saturated calomel electrode) in volts and interfacial tension in dynes per cm. for various concentrations of propionic acid.

In presence of 0.1 M KCl			In presence of 0.1 M KBr		
Concn. of acid	Interfacial tension	$E_{e.c.m.}$	Conc. of acid	Interfacial tension	$E_{e.c.m.}$
0.525 M	414.4	0.415	0.228 M	419.7	0.500
1.070 M	408.0	0.385	0.296 M	418.0	0.485
1.479 M	402.3	0.382	0.469 M	414.6	0.482
2.011 M	399.4	0.365	0.728 M	410.8	0.460
3.004 M	396.5	0.358	0.847 M	408.1	0.455
3.542 M	395.1	0.355			

From equation (2), at constant activity of potassium salt, since (2), is a complete differential, we get

$$\left(\frac{\partial q}{\partial \mu} \right)_{\Gamma, P, T} = \left(\frac{\partial \Gamma_{org}}{\partial E^-} \right)_{\mu, P, T} \quad \dots (7)$$

Since the dissociation constant of the acid is small ($= 1.4 \times 10^{-5}$), activity of the acid is replaced by concentration. At the point of inflexion, therefore $\left(\frac{\partial q}{\partial E^-} \right) = 0$ for all concentrations of organic acid as is seen from figures 5 and 6. It follows therefore that variation of surface excess of organic acid with potential should be maximum for this value of

FIG 5

potential for all concentrations of organic acid. In other words, value of E^- at the point of inflexion corresponds to maximum adsorption. At the corresponding value of $q^M (= -2\mu$

FIG. 6

coulombs cm^{-2}), it is obvious that maximum adsorption of organic acid takes place at the interface. Surface excess of organic acid (Γ) at the interface was evaluated from graphical differentiation of $\gamma - RT \ln C_{acid}$ plots at constant E_{cal} . Variations of Γ_{acid} with concentration and E^- are shown in figures 5 and 6 for KCl base solution, and in figures 7 and 8 for KBr system respectively. Adsorption isotherms as shown in figures 5 and 7 do not show any saturation for the concentrations of acids used. The maximum value of Γ_{org} obtained in this investigation corresponds to about 90% coverage of the surface, assuming that the organic acid is adsorbed with the molecule lying perpendicular to the mercury surface and the cross sectional area is 21 \AA^2 . It is thus clear that even at these high concentrations complete coverage of the surface does not take place.

We are thankful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the award of a Jr. Research Fellowship to one of us (M.R.B.) during the tenure of this work.

FIG 7

FIG. 8